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Learning of complex concepts Engineering students' developing epistemic fluency in an electric circuit theory course

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ABSTRACT

An important aim in engineering education is that students should not only acquire knowledge, but they should be able to use this knowledge in action. I.e. they should develop professional capabilities for knowledgeable action and actionable knowledge.

According to Markauskaite and Goodyear professional knowledgeable action requires a holistic, fluent and co-ordinated use of semiotic and material tools, body and environment. Knowledgeable action requires the development of epistemic fluency that involves the ability to smoothly move between abstract, contextual and situated ways of knowing and the capacity to employ multiple epistemic tools. However, the epistemic complexity of knowledgeable action is often underestimated in engineering education. This epistemic complexity has been addressed by Carstensen and Bernhard who have developed the notion of “learning of complex concepts” (LCC-model) that models how students learn to master epistemic tools by “making links”.

In this study we have used the LCC-model as an investigatory tool to analyse video-recordings from electric circuit theory courses. The aim was to gain an increased understanding in how students develop epistemic fluency. We will discuss critical features in the design of labs and in the use of real experiments, computer simulations, modelling and other semiotic and material tools in labs for students' development of epistemic fluency. The results of this study show that labs can be designed to facilitate students' development of epistemic fluency by making links.

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1 INTRODUCTION

An important objective in engineering education is that students should *learn to use* theories and models. The aim is that students should not only acquire knowledge, they should also be able to use their knowledge and skills in action. Indeed, Mitcham [1] notes that design “constitutes the essence of engineering” since an engineer is “concerned with how things *ought* to be ... to *attain* goals and to *function*” [2]. Thus, as pointed out by Skolimowski [3], science and engineering differ in important aspects. Simply put, the aim of science is to produce theories, laws and models that describe some aspects of (idealized) reality. On the other hand the aim of engineering is to design technical artefacts (i.e. products, processes or systems) and arrive at “artefact proposals” [4]. The proposed technical artefacts are human-made physical objects, but they are also intentional objects designed to perform some function in order to achieve some goals [5]. To be able to design, students should develop an understanding of the *relation* between theories and models, and objects and events, and to develop holistic, conceptual knowledge [6]. This is often seen as the fundamental purpose of lab work [7]. During lab-work, students are expected to *use*, or *learn to use*, symbolic and physical tools (such as concepts, theories, models, representations, inscriptions, mathematics, instruments and devices) in order both to understand the phenomena being studied, and to develop the skills and abilities to use the tools themselves [8], i.e. they should develop a holistic, fluent and co-ordinated use of semiotic and material tools, body and environment [9]. This requires development of epistemic fluency [9, 10] that involves the ability to smoothly move between abstract, contextual and situated ways of knowing and the capacity to employ multiple epistemic tools.

All this implies that students during their education should develop professional capabilities for “knowledgeable action” and acquire “actionable knowledge” as pointed out by Markauskaite and Goodyear [9]. It is important to note the two aspects of knowledge. *Actionable knowledge* means that the knowledge students (and engineers) possess should have such qualities that they are able to use it in professional action. On the other hand, *knowledgeable action* stresses that action should be based on knowledge – in a specific action it is not a simple task to understand which knowledge to use and adapt the knowledge to the situation at hand [cf. 11, 12]. A problem, according to Markauskaite and Goodyear [9], is that the “epistemic complexity of knowledgeable action is underestimated” and “higher education sometimes oversimplifies the epistemic qualities of professional tools”. This epistemic complexity has been addressed by Carstensen and Bernhard who have developed the notion of “learning of complex concepts” (LCC-model) [13-16] that models how students “make links”, and thus learn to master epistemic tools [17].

In this study we have used the LCC-model as an investigatory tool to analyse video-recordings from electric circuit theory courses. The aim was to use the LCC-model to gain an increased understanding in how students develop epistemic fluency.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the background and the setting of the study; Section 3 describes the theoretical framework and the qualitative methodology used, i.e. video-recording, epistemic fluency and learning of complex concepts; Section 4 presents the findings of the current study; finally, Section 5 presents a short conclusion.

2 BACKGROUND AND SETTING

2.1 Setting

The empirical data analysed and discussed in this study was obtained in two consecutive years in an electric circuit theory course for electrical engineering students. The particular focus in this paper will be on students' courses of action in the first, original version, of a lab on the topic of transient response and students' courses of action in the re-designed version of the lab the following year. In previous publications the design and re-design of tasks using variation theory [18], the use of design science to develop theory and methodology concurrently with the designing of the lab [16], and the inclusion of simulations in the re-designed lab to achieve synergetic learning effects [19, 20] have been reported. In the present study a special emphasis will instead be on the question of students' development of epistemic fluency through their participation in the two different versions of the transient response lab.

2.2 The Lab: Transient Response

The circuit analysed in this lab is shown in Fig. 1a. Measured graphs for the current $i(t)$ through the circuit are shown in Fig. 1b. The input voltage $u_{in}(t)$ is a 1 V step (practically achieved by a square wave with low frequency). L and C are kept constant and the value of R is varied.

Fig. 1. a.) The electric circuit investigated in the transient response lab. R_{coil} is the internal resistance of the inductor. b.) Measured curves for the current $i(t)$ for different values of $R_{resistor}$ ($L=8.2$ mH and $C=100$ μ F) when the input voltage is a unit step.

The circuit in Fig. 1a is a second order system and if the current $i(t)$ is taken as the output signal and the voltage $u_{in}(t)$ as the input signal the transfer function will be

$$G(s) = \frac{1}{L} \cdot \frac{s}{s^2 + \frac{R}{L}s + \frac{1}{LC}} \quad (1)$$

The step response of the current through the circuit ($t > 0$) takes the form $i(t) = a \cdot e^{-bt} \cdot \sin(c \cdot t)$ or $i(t) = a \cdot (e^{-bt} - e^{-ct})$, depending on whether the roots of the characteristic polynomial of eq. (1) $s^2 + s \cdot R_{tot}/L + 1/(LC)$ are complex conjugated or real. Thus, if L and C are constant, the form depends on the relative values of R_{tot} and $2\sqrt{L/C}$.²

One of the explicit tasks posed in this lab was for the students to make a curve fit to the measured graphs (See Fig. 2a.) of the current through the circuit for various values

² A third form is also possible: $i(t) = a \cdot te^{-bt}$ (critical damping). However, this occurs only if R_{tot} is exactly equal to $2\sqrt{L/C}$, which is very unlikely in practice.

of R . This basically comes down to find an appropriate mathematical expression to cause a calculated graph to give the same curve as the measured graph, and to show both in the same figure. It was possible to do this in the same computer program – *Data Studio*[®] – that was used to control the computer interface that generated the input voltage to the circuit and measured the current through the circuit and the output voltage.

Fig. 2. a.) Fitting of a calculated graph (solid line) to a measured graph. The function used can be seen in the rectangle “User Defined” in the centre of the figure (In this case $i(t)=0.12e^{-420t}\sin[1100t]$ A) b.) Curves from Simulink-simulation for three different transfer functions (see Table 2 below).

From the curve fit students were expected to be able to determine the experimental values of R_{tot} , L and C for the circuit.

Table 1. Expected values for the roots of the characteristic polynomial of eq. (1) and corresponding expected values of $i(t)$ for varying values of R_{res} , with L , C , and the step voltage constant. The resistance of the coil is assumed to be 6Ω . Note that the frequency, ω_d , of the damped system changes with R and is not equal to ω_n .

R_{res} (Ω)	R_{tot} (Ω)	L (mH)	C (μ F)	Roots of $s^2 + \frac{R_{tot}}{L}s + \frac{1}{LC}$	$i(t)$ (A) ($t > 0$) (A)
0	6	8.2	100	$-366+1042j$ $-366-1042j$	$0.1170e^{-366t}\sin(1042t)$
10	16	8.2	100	$-976+517j$ $-976-517j$	$0.2357e^{-976t}\sin(517t)$
33	39	8.2	100	-272 -4484	$0.0290(e^{-272t} - e^{-4484t})$
100	106	8.2	100	-95 -12832	$0.0096(e^{-95t} - e^{-12832t})$

In a revised version of the lab simulations using Simulink[®] were used. In line with Variation theory [21, 22] the transfer functions were systematically varied. For example, three forms for the denominator were used

$$G(s) = \frac{N(s)}{s^2 + 2s + 5} \tag{2}$$

$$G(s) = \frac{N(s)}{s^2 + 2s + 1} \tag{3}$$

$$G(s) = \frac{N(s)}{s^2 + 2s + 0.75} \tag{4}$$

with complex-conjugated roots [eq. (2)], a double root [eq. (3)], and two real roots [eq. (4)] respectively. As numerator 5, 3s and 3s + 5 were used. The step responses for some of the transfer functions are shown in Table 2 and in Fig. 2b. Note that the denominators in this case have rather simple roots easy to calculate by hand.

Table 2. Some transfer functions used in the Simulink simulations and the corresponding step responses (See Fig. 2b for graphs).

Transfer function	Roots of the denominator	Step response ($t > 0$)
$G_1 = \frac{3s}{s^2 + 2s + 5}$	$-1 \pm 2j$	$y_1(t) = \frac{3}{2} \cdot e^{-t} \cdot \sin(2t)$
$G_2 = \frac{3s}{s^2 + 2s + 1}$	$-1, -1$	$y_2(t) = 3t \cdot e^{-t}$
$G_3 = \frac{3s}{s^2 + 2s + 0.75}$	$-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{3}{2}$	$y_3(t) = 3 \cdot (e^{-\frac{1}{2}t} - e^{-\frac{3}{2}t})$

3 THEORY AND METHOD

3.1 Data Collection

Video have been used to record and study students' courses of actions [23] during the two versions of the transient response labs (See section 2.2). I.e. we have analyzed what the students did do, what resources they used, what they made relevant, and how they oriented themselves towards the object of learning. Each lab-group (comprising 2-3 students) was recorded using a digital camcorder, obtaining a total of 80 h of video from the original and the re-designed versions of the transient response lab. The data was subsequently used to detect typical interaction patterns using the LCC-model (See section 3.3) and to study the development of epistemic fluency (See section 3.2).

3.2 Epistemic Fluency

A fundamental aspect of investigating how students learn and how they use knowledge in action is to study their deliberate use of epistemic tools in activities. An epistemic tool is a conceptual, symbolic or physical tool purposefully used as a “tool of knowing” [24]. Consequently, Markauskaite and Goodyear [9] have argued that one aspect of learning is “learning through mastering epistemic tools”.

As already mentioned above a problem is that the “epistemic complexity of knowledgeable action is underestimated” and “higher education sometimes oversimplifies the epistemic qualities of professional tools”. Rather, according to Markauskaite and Goodyear [9], professional knowledgeable action requires “fluent use of semiotic and material tools, body and environment”. This requires, they argue, the weaving together, blending and co-ordination of conceptual, physical, epistemological and symbolic resources to establish an epistemic space. Thus, the concept of *epistemic fluency* [9, 10] is seen as involving “both an *ability to move smoothly* between the abstract, contextual and situated ways of knowing and a *capacity to employ multiple ways of knowing* provided by the senses, environment and imagination to construct actionable understanding” [9].

3.3 Learning of Complex Concepts Model (LCC-model)

The capacity to employ multiple ways of knowing has previously been investigated by Carstensen and Bernhard in the context of labs in electrical engineering [18]. From analysis of video recordings of students' courses of actions [23] they constructed what they called the "learning of complex concepts" (LCC-model) [13-16]. In this model identified epistemic objects are illustrated by circles and the links between these epistemic objects the studied lab-group were able to make during the lab are illustrated by arrows. Figures 3a, 3b, 4a and 4b below are made using the LCC-model analyzing students' courses of actions in the two versions of the transient response lab described above. The shaded circles in the figure represent epistemic objects located in the "world" of objects/events and the other circles the "world" of theories/models according to a categorization proposed by Tiberghien [25]. In the LCC-model learning can be seen as the making of these links by students. An implication is that learning, knowledge and understanding is not seen as an either/or thing. Rather, learning is seen as becoming "richer" the more links that are established and kept in focal awareness simultaneously.

4 RESULTS

4.1 First version of the transient response lab

As mentioned above, in section 2.2, one of the tasks in the lab was to make a curve fit to the experimental curves for $i(t)$ (see Fig. 1b and 2a) for varied values of R_{res} and from the curve fit determine the values for R , L , and C in the circuit. The fitting turned out to be a very difficult task for most students as it requires that the students identify what type of function the different curves in Fig. 1b correspond to. However, although the students in practice only had two functions to choose from they used all types of functions as an onset. Analysis of the videotapes revealed that students, the first year, during the lab mostly worked with one concept/entity (see Fig. 3a) at a time. Students avoided, or postponed, to do the necessary mathematics, i.e. mathematics was to a limited extent used as an epistemic tool. A more detailed analysis revealed that, when making curve fits, students only focused separately – one at the time – on the measured graphs, the calculated graph from the curve fit, and the function used to make the curve fit (See Fig. 3b). No links were made to the transfer function.

Fig. 3. a) Links made by the students in the first version of the transient lab. b) Students' focus when making curve fits using *mathematical functions* to model the response in the time-domain in the first version of the lab.

In the first version of the transient lab the task structure also followed the circular path displayed in Fig. 3a. Consequently, students' learning trajectories followed this pathway. As is discussed earlier students had difficulties to mathematically model the step response in an appropriate way and to draw conclusions from their model. Although the *intended* object of learning was that they should be able to make a link between the measured and calculated graphs this was not apparent in the task structure. Actually, as can be seen in Fig. 3a it was only possible for students to make links between the object/event and the theory/model world at two places.

4.2 Revised version of the transient response lab

Classroom observations and the video-recordings revealed that the students participating in the revised version of the lab, used the following year, worked in a rather different way as is indicated in Fig. 4a. The Simulink simulations enabled students to see where they were heading with the mathematics as the simulation outputs had similar forms as the experimental curves.

Our analysis is that the inclusion of simulations enabled the students to establish a triangular route between the *measured graph*, the *calculated graph*, and the *transfer function* and another triangular route between the *calculated graph*, the *function in the time-domain*, and the *transfer function* as is shown in Fig 4b. As a result the students were not afraid of the mathematics and started to calculate from the beginning. The discussions were centred on the underlying content of the lab. During the lab students noticed the relationships between different experimental graphs instead of looking only at one curve at a time. Throughout the lab they made links between the epistemic objects and at the end of the lab all the observed students had made the links displayed in Fig. 4a.

Fig. 4. a) Links made by the students during the revised lab. The numbers assigned to links refer to their entry in Table 3, and do not indicate any order in their establishment. b) Triangular routes enabled by the inclusion of simulations in the revised version of the lab.

To illustrate the complexity of the epistemic actions performed by the students in the revised lab the links displayed in Fig 4a have been labelled and assigned a number (This number is for representative purposes only and do not indicate any order in making of links. Indeed, the order in which links were established were different for different students.). In Table 3 a short description of what students typically do to establish the links in Fig 4a is presented.

Table 3. Short descriptions of the different epistemic actions students had to perform during the revised transient response lab to make each of the links displayed in Fig. 4a.

No.	Link		Label	Short description of students' epistemic actions to make the link.
	From	To		
1	Real circuit	Differential equation	Physical modelling	Model the current through circuit using differential equations.
2	Differential equation	Transfer function (s-domain)	Mathematical transformation	Apply Laplace transforms to the differential equation.
3	Real circuit	Transfer function (s-domain)	Physical modelling	Model the circuit directly using Laplace transforms to obtain the transfer function in the s-domain (frequency domain).
4	Transfer function (s-domain)	Real circuit	Realisation	Use the transfer function obtained through fitting to the measured graph to calculate corresponding values for R, L and C.
5	Transfer function (s-domain)	Function in the time-domain	Mathematical transformation	Inverse transform the transfer function to obtain (possible) function in the time-domain.
6	Function in the time-domain	Transfer function (s-domain)	Mathematical transformation	Laplace transform the function in the time-domain to obtain the transfer function.
7	Calculated graph in the time-domain	Function in the time-domain	Interpret	Interpretation and judgement how the parameters of the function in the time-domain should be adjusted to fit to the measured graph.
8	Function in the time-domain	Calculated graph in the time-domain	Draw	Draw a graph of the time-domain function.
9	Calculated graph in the time-domain	Measured graph in the time-domain	Fitting	Fit the calculated graph to the measured graph.
10	Measured graph in the time-domain	Calculated graph in the time-domain	Interpret	Interpretation and judgement how the calculated graph should be adjusted to fit to the measured graph. Is the fit "good enough".
11	Real circuit	Measured graph in the time-domain	Collection of data	Connect sensors and measurement equipment to the circuit. Setup and run data collection.
12	Measured graph in the time-domain	Real circuit	Qualitative interpretation	Adjust setup of data collection to obtain as good data as possible.
13	Measured graph in the time-domain	Transfer function (s-domain)	Qualitative judgement	Judge and interpret the measured graph in relation to the transfer function
14	Transfer function (s-domain)	Calculated graph in the time-domain	Simulation	Use Simulink to directly obtain calculated graphs from transfer functions
15	Calculated graph in the time-domain	Transfer function (s-domain)	Qualitative judgement	Judge and interpret the calculated graph in relation to the transfer function

In this short paper it is not possible to give a full description of all the epistemic actions students had to do to make all the links presented in Fig. 4a and Table 3. Nevertheless, the empirical results summarized and presented in Fig. 4a and Table 3 clearly display

the complexity of the actions students are supposed to perform to make links and to be seen as understanding transient response in an electric circuit.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results reveal that during the first version of the transient response lab students develop a quite limited epistemic fluency revealed through the few links students made as is shown in figure 3a.

On the other hand the results from the revised lab as presented in Fig. 4a and Table 3, indeed, reveal the truth in Markauskaite and Goodyear [9], statement about the “epistemic complexity of knowledgeable action”. The analysis made, using the LCC-model, clearly presents the complexity of learning. It is also clear that the students have some mastery in the fluent use of epistemic tools. However, it is important to note that this epistemic fluency does not come by itself. It was a result of a deliberate re-design of the lab (See the triangular routes in Fig. 4b) with an intention to facilitate the integrated use of different epistemic tools, especially regarding making links transcending the object/event and theory/model worlds.

We argue that fluent use of epistemic tools involving the “fluent use of semiotic and material tools, body and environment” [9] is important for professional knowledgeable action in all branches of engineering. In another study [26] we have demonstrated how architectural engineering students are using practical epistemic cognition in a design project and that they had developed epistemic fluency. The students in that study used a wealth of bodily material resources as epistemic tools, in an integrated and seamless way, as part of their interactions to design an energy optimized building.

Finally, this study reveals the similarities between the idea of mastering of epistemic tools by “making links” proposed by Carstensen and Bernhard [17] and the notion of “epistemic fluency” by Markauskaite and Goodyear [9]. We propose that these similarities should further be investigated as we see a potential for mutual cross-fertilization between theories.

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